

ANIDRA (PRIMARY INSOMNIA): A CRITICAL REVIEW WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AYURVEDIC PATHOGENESIS AND MANAGEMENT

*¹Dr. Devender Kasushik, ²Dr. Darshana

*¹PhD Scholar, Desh Bhagat Ayurvedic College and Univaesity Mandi Gobindgarh Punjab.

²Assiciate Professor KC Dept DBU Mandi Gobindgarh Punjab.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Devender Kaushik

PhD Scholar, Desh Bhagat Ayurvedic
College and Univaesity Mandi
Gobindgarh Punjab.

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ABSTRACT

Sleep disturbances are increasingly recognized as a major public health concern worldwide, largely attributed to psychological stress, irregular lifestyles, and excessive digital exposure. In Ayurveda, the condition of disturbed or absent sleep is described as *Anidra*. Contemporary medical science classifies Primary Insomnia as a disorder characterized by persistent difficulty in initiating or maintaining sleep. Ayurveda interprets this condition as an imbalance of the *Vata* and *Pitta Doshas*, which disturbs the physiological equilibrium of *Trayopastambha* (the three fundamental pillars of life: diet, sleep, and regulated lifestyle). The present review evaluates the etiological factors, pathogenesis, and therapeutic approaches of *Anidra* described in classical Ayurvedic literature and compares them with modern scientific perspectives. Special emphasis is placed on the role of *Medhya Rasayana* (neurocognitive rejuvenating herbs) and external therapeutic procedures such as *Shirodhara* and *Padabhyanga*. Evidence from both traditional

texts and modern studies suggests that Ayurvedic interventions may provide a holistic and sustainable approach for the management of insomnia without the risk of pharmacological dependency.

KEYWORDS: Anidra, Insomnia, Vata Dosha, Shirodhara, Medhya Rasayana, Ayurvedic Management.

INTRODUCTION

Sleep (*Nidra*) is regarded in Ayurveda as one of the three essential supports of life, collectively referred to as *Trayopastambha*. Proper sleep is necessary for maintaining physical vitality, mental stability, and longevity. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe that balanced sleep contributes to nourishment of body tissues (*Dhatus*), maintenance of digestive strength, and equilibrium of *Doshas*.^[1]

Disturbance or absence of sleep is termed *Anidra*, which is considered a significant etiological factor for several physical and psychological disorders.^[2]

In modern medicine, Primary Insomnia is defined as persistent dissatisfaction with sleep quantity or quality, characterized by difficulty in sleep initiation, difficulty maintaining sleep, or early morning awakening without identifiable medical causes.^[3]

Epidemiological studies indicate that approximately 10–15% of adults suffer from chronic insomnia, while 30–35% experience temporary sleep disturbances during their lifetime.^[4] In India, the prevalence of insomnia is increasing due to rapid urbanization and stressful lifestyles, with studies reporting that nearly 18% of the urban population experiences symptoms related to insomnia.^[5]

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1. To review the classical Ayurvedic description of *Anidra*.
2. To correlate Ayurvedic concepts of *Anidra* with Primary Insomnia described in modern medicine.
3. To evaluate Ayurvedic therapeutic measures used for the management of sleep disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a narrative review based on classical Ayurvedic literature and contemporary scientific publications.

Primary Ayurvedic references were obtained from classical compendia including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*. Modern scientific data related to insomnia were collected from biomedical databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and the AYUSH Research Portal.

Relevant peer-reviewed articles and authoritative texts were analyzed to understand the etiopathogenesis and treatment approaches of insomnia from both Ayurvedic and modern perspectives.

DISCUSSION

SAMPRAPTI OF ANIDRA

According to Ayurveda, sleep is primarily influenced by the balance of *Kapha Dosha* and the mental quality known as *Tamas*. When these stabilizing factors decline and are replaced by aggravated *Vata* and *Pitta*, normal sleep mechanisms become disturbed.

Major Causative Factors

- Excessive mental stress
- Irregular diet and lifestyle
- Night-time awakening
- Excessive use of digital devices
- Consumption of dry, spicy, and stimulating foods

SAMPRAPTI

This pathophysiology resembles the theory described in modern sleep research, where excessive activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis results in persistent wakefulness.^[6]

Several Ayurvedic herbs possess sedative, anxiolytic, and neuroprotective properties that help restore sleep balance.

- **Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*)**

This herb is known for its stress-reducing and adaptogenic properties. Studies indicate that it reduces cortisol levels and improves sleep quality in individuals with stress-related insomnia.^[7]

- **Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*)**

Brahmi acts as a *Medhya Rasayana* that enhances cognitive function and reduces anxiety, thereby facilitating mental relaxation and better sleep.^[8]

- **Jatamansi (*Nardostachys jatamansi*)**

Traditionally used as a sleep-inducing herb, Jatamansi increases levels of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), promoting sedation and relaxation.^[9]

- **Tagara (*Valeriana wallichii*)**

Tagara has mild sedative properties and acts by modulating GABA receptors in the central nervous system, which helps induce natural sleep.^[10]

TREATMENT IN AYURVEDA

Ayurveda recommends a combination of internal medicines and external therapeutic procedures for the management of Anidra.

SHIRODHARA

Shirodhara involves the continuous pouring of warm medicated oil on the forehead in a rhythmic manner. Clinical observations suggest that this therapy produces relaxation, improves parasympathetic activity, and may influence pineal gland function responsible for melatonin secretion.^[11]

PADABHYANGA

Padabhyanga refers to therapeutic massage of the feet using medicated oils or ghee. This therapy is believed to stabilize *Vata Dosha*, reduce nervous tension, and improve sleep quality.^[12]

PATHYA AND APATHYA**PATHYA****Diet**

- Warm milk with nutmeg
- Milk and ghee preparations
- Light and easily digestible evening meals

Lifestyle

- Maintaining regular sleep-wake cycles
- Meditation and breathing exercises (Pranayama)
- Avoiding excessive mental work at night

APATHYA (To Be Avoided)**Diet**

- Excessively spicy or dry foods
- Caffeine and stimulants at night

Lifestyle

- Late-night screen exposure
- Suppression of natural urges
- Irregular sleeping habits

CONCLUSION

Anidra represents a complex disorder involving both physiological and psychological components. While modern pharmacological treatments may provide temporary symptomatic relief, prolonged use of sedative medications often leads to dependence and adverse effects.

Ayurvedic management focuses on restoring systemic balance through herbal medications, lifestyle regulation, and therapeutic procedures. These interventions aim to correct the underlying imbalance of *Doshas* and promote natural sleep.

Therefore, integrating Ayurvedic principles with modern clinical understanding may offer a comprehensive and sustainable approach to the management of Primary Insomnia.

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